

Welded hybrid steel box-section girders subjected to pure bending and bending-shear interaction

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ABSTRACT

In civil engineering, high-strength steel materials, namely steel grades ranging from S500 up to S960, are increasingly gaining recognition, particularly in the construction of large-span bridges and high-rise buildings. When it comes to bridges, a cost-effective and efficient solution involves using hybrid girders that incorporate both low-strength and high-strength steel materials. Typically, these hybrid girders feature low-strength steel webs and high-strength steel flanges. In Europe, aside from some limited practical applications and research outcomes in Sweden and Spain, these types of structures are pioneering solutions in bridge engineering. Notably, the current European design standards lack the theoretical background and practical guide for their strength and stability design. To determine the theoretical background of this girder type and to develop the design theories for application purposes a large-scale experimental research program is designed and carried out focusing on the bending and bending-shear interaction resistance of hybrid steel box-sections. 14 welded hybrid steel box-section beams are tested with varying geometry, six of them against pure bending and eight against combination of bending and shear. The flanges of the examined hybrid girders are made of S700 or S500, the web of the specimens consists of S355 steel grade. Two control specimens were homogenous girders made of S355 and S700. The details of the experiments and the results such as resistances, failure modes, stress- and displacement curves are presented and discussed in this paper.

Keywords: large-scale experiment, hybrid steel girder, high strength steel, moment and moment-shear resistance

1 INTRODUCTION

Steel beams are widely used as primary structural elements in various civil engineering applications, such as bridges and buildings. Recently, hybrid steel beams have gained attention as an innovative approach to optimize the use of steel materials and improve the structural performance of steel beams. A hybrid steel beam typically consists of webs made of low-strength steel and flanges made of high-strength steel, which allows for the efficient use of materials with different mechanical properties to achieve enhanced structural performance. In recent years, there has been growing interest in studying the behaviour of hybrid steel beams under bending and shear through experimental testing, numerical simulations, and analytical modelling. These studies aim to investigate the structural performance of hybrid steel beams, including their ultimate and serviceability limit states, as well as their failure mechanisms and deformation characteristics. Understanding the behaviour of hybrid steel beams is crucial for their safe and efficient design in practical engineering applications. In order to establish the theoretical foundations of this type of girder and develop design theories for practical purposes, it is necessary to conduct experimental laboratory test programs. The primary objective of this research program is to conduct experimental

tests on hybrid steel beams with various configurations and loading conditions, that can be served as a basis for numerical simulations and analytical modelling to gain insights into the structural performance of hybrid steel beams. The current paper summarises the experimental research program executed at the Budapest University of Technology and Economics Department of Structural Engineering in 2023.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW – HYBRID STEEL GIRDERS

Hybrid steel girders are characterized by their unique design where the flanges possess higher yield strength than the web. This innovative configuration aims to capitalize on the advantages of high-strength materials while maintaining a cost-effective and efficient design. The concept of hybrid steel girders started to emerge from 1940s (1–3), but until the 2000's the research progress was slow, and the hybrid girders were mainly used and researched only in the USA. In the 2000's and especially in the 2010's when new HSS steels are developed the interest and therefore the research on hybrid beams has seen a significant increase, the number of studies has increased mainly in Asia and Europe (4–11).

Regarding the bending resistance of hybrid girder one of the earliest investigations is made by Veljkovic and Johansson (2). The authors stated that the bending resistance is influenced by the difference in yield strength between flanges and webs. The web will be partially yielded before the flanges reach their yield strength. The influence of this fact will be different for different cross-section classes. Therefore, different design models are proposed for different cross-section classes. For cross-section classes 1-2, the bending resistance is calculated from a fully yielded cross-section. In the case of cross-section class 3, the bending resistance can be calculated from the assumption, that the flanges can reach their yield strength, the web comes in partial plastic situation which plasticism can be considered in the bending resistance calculation. In the case of class 4 cross-sections, a specific stress distribution can be considered, and the bending resistance should be calculated by considering partial plastic stress distribution within the web – even if it buckles. Another investigation is made by Lateef et al. (13) recommended the limit value of $h_w/t_w=120$ for class 4 cross-section. The bending resistance of class 1-3 cross-section beams were also analysed by Zhu et al. (14) experimentally and numerically. The experimental investigations were extended by numerical simulations performing a large numerical parametric study to investigate the bending resistance of HSS and hybrid girders separately. Based on their investigations it was confirmed that the current slenderness limits for class 2 and 3 cross-sections according to EN1993-1-1 are suitable to classify the outstand flanges (in compression) and internal webs (in bending) of both HSS homogeneous and hybrid welded I-sections. To satisfy the rotation capacity requirement of the Eurocode design principles, stricter Class 1 slenderness limits for outstand flanges in compression (i.e. $b_f/t_f \leq 8$) and internal webs in bending ($h_w/t_w \leq 60$) were proposed. Furthermore, both the experimental and numerical results proved the accuracy of the above presented bending resistance calculation methods for beams having class 1-3 cross-sections. Detailed analysis of class 4 cross-sections is still missing from the international literature.

Regarding the shear buckling resistance, there is a limited number of previous results investigating the ultimate behaviour of hybrid girders. Large number of investigations were conducted analysing the effect of the flange contribution in the shear buckling resistance, which contains the yield strength of the web. These investigations need extensions and the current design methods might need improvement based on the analysis results.

To overcome the lack of detailed investigations on the class 4 cross-section's bending (M), shear buckling (V) and M-V interaction resistance of hybrid girders, an extensive experimental and numerical research program is designed and partially executed. As a first step, the results of the experimental investigations are presented and evaluated in this paper.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCESS AND TEST SPECIMENS

The presented experimental program was carried out in the Structural Engineering Laboratory of the BME Department of Structural Engineering. Prior to the experimental tests a detailed shape capturing (imperfection) measurement was carried out on all the specimens in order to accurately determine the actual shape and imperfections of the specimens. The introduction of the measurement method is not part of this paper, the shape-measuring process and its results is under publication in an individual paper. After the loading tests, coupon specimens were cut-out from the failed specimens and material tests are carried out in order to accurately determine the original material behaviour of the plates that the load experimental specimens were composed of. The presentation of the details of the material tests and their results is presented in *Chapter 5*. Within the experimental research program altogether 14 large-scale specimens were examined, six of them are loaded by pure bending, these are referred as M-type specimens, and eight of them are loaded by interaction of bending and shear, these are referred as MV-type specimens. First, the six M-type specimens are tested, then the 8 MV-type specimens, because the experimental set-up was different between the two different loading scenarios. The tested specimens are summarized in *Table 1*. The referencing code of the specimens are consisting of the following parts:

- BOX – all test specimens are box-sections,
- # (one digit number) – thickness of the web in mm,
- code for steel grades:
 - 355 – homogenous section with S355 steel grade,
 - 700 – homogenous section with S700 steel grade,
 - H0 – hybrid section, web is S355, flanges are S700 steel grade,
 - H1 – hybrid section, web is S355, flanges are S500 steel grade,
- loading type:
 - M – M-type specimens with pure moment loading,
 - MV – MV-type specimens with loading of combination of moment-shear,
- # (number) – for MV-type specimens the length of the specimen in m.

Table 1. Investigated specimens

Loading type	Specimen code	thickness of web t_w [mm]	thickness of upper flange, t_{uf} [mm]	thickness of lower flange, t_{lf} [mm]	reference length, L [mm]
M-type	BOX4-355-M	4	10	10	1000
	BOX4-700-M	4	10	12	1000
	BOX4-H1-M	4	10	10	1000
	BOX4-H0-M	4	10	12	1000
	BOX6-H0-M	6	10	12	1000
	BOX8-H0-M	8	10	12	1000
MV-type	BOX4-H0-MV1	4	10	12	1000
	BOX4-H0-MV1.5	4	10	12	1500
	BOX4-H0-MV2	4	10	12	2000
	BOX4-H0-MV3	4	10	12	3000
	BOX8-H0-MV1	8	10	12	1000
	BOX8-H0-MV1.5	8	10	12	1500
	BOX8-H0-MV2	8	10	12	2000
	BOX8-H0-MV3	8	10	12	3000

All the 14 specimens are box-section beams, the cross-section is shown in *Fig. 1 a)*. The same geometry is used for each specimens, only the thickness of the web is varied between specimens as shown in *Table 1* and the thickness of the bottom flange is varied between some specimens. Generally, the thickness of the lower flange is 12 mm for most of the specimens, but in case of a

few cases this was replaced by 10 mm thickness due to manufacturing issues. All the geometrical data is summarized in *Table 1*. The height of the web is 480 mm, the width of the flanges is 320 mm, the inner distance between the webs is 230 mm. The end-configuration is different between M-type and MV-type specimens. For M-type specimens there is a 30 mm thick endplate at both ends. During the test set-up, the test specimen is connected to other loading elements through these endplates by bolts. For the MV-type specimens, there is the same endplate at one end of the beam to connect it to another loading element, but the other end is supported at its bottom edge during the test set-up. In the supported cross-section a 15 mm thick diaphragm is located. The specimen was manufactured 180 mm longer measured from the support cross-section and another 15 mm thick diaphragm is placed at the end cross-section. The general layout of the specimens in a top and side view is shown in *Fig. 1 c*). The connection holes in the endplates are predrilled in their exact positions according to *Fig. 1 a*).

Fig. 1. a) Cross-section of specimens; b) Geometry of endplate; c) Side view and top view of specimens

The planned nominal geometrical data is shown in *Fig. 1 a*) and in *Table 1*, but the actual real geometry could differ from these. The actual thickness of all the main plates of the specimens was measured with ultrasonic thickness measuring device. Each unique plate was measured 10 times, the measurements referred as t_i , where $i = 1..10$, and the real thickness was considered as the average of the measured values not considering the highest and lowest values according to *Eq. (1)*.

$$t_{real} = \frac{\sum t_i - \min(t_i) - \max(t_i)}{8}, \quad i = 1..10 \quad (1)$$

Based on this evaluation the obtained thicknesses are summarized in *Table 2*. The specimens' cross-section is symmetrical along the vertical axis based on the planned nominal values, but if we consider the real thicknesses and the real imperfection then the two webs should be differentiated from each other. Therefore, all the unique plates of the specimens were named, the two webs are referred as W1 and W2, the upper flange is called as F1 and the lower flange as F2. This labelling is used in *Table 2* and later in this paper. The full length of the M-type specimens is also measured and shown in *Table 2*. The real global geometrical dimensions of the specimens such as the length of the specimens, height of the web, width of the flange etc. proved to be accurate compared to the planned nominal values, therefore, for all the future evaluation these geometrical data are considered to be equal as the nominal values. During the test set-up the specimens are connected to loading beams that are stronger than the specimens, therefore these elements don't fail during testing and the same elements can be used for all test set-up. These loading elements are similar then the MV-type specimens but having an $L = 3500$ mm reference length and slightly different cross-section with thicker plates. The two loading elements are labelled as BOX-T (A) and BOX-T (B). The real measured thicknesses of the plates of the loading beams are also shown in *Table 2*. The steel grade of the BOX-T elements is S355.

Table 2. Measured geometrical data of specimens

Loading type	Specimen code	thickness of web W1, t_{W1} [mm]	thickness of web W2, t_{W2} [mm]	thickness of upper flange, t_{F1} [mm]	thickness of lower flange, t_{F2} [mm]	reference length, L [mm]
M-type	BOX4-355-M	3.991	3.985	9.956	9.960	996
	BOX4-700-M	4.008	4.011	9.965	11.929	995
	BOX4-H1-M	3.956	3.941	9.935	9.921	997
	BOX4-H0-M	3.923	3.933	9.943	11.888	996
	BOX6-H0-M	6.030	6.020	9.953	11.934	995
	BOX8-H0-M	7.718	7.736	9.888	11.945	994
MV-type	BOX4-H0-MV1	3.983	3.963	9.958	11.928	
	BOX4-H0-MV1.5	3.954	3.958	9.888	11.953	
	BOX4-H0-MV2	3.916	3.944	9.954	11.891	
	BOX4-H0-MV3	3.901	3.933	9.930	11.953	
	BOX8-H0-MV1	7.750	7.780	9.978	11.978	
	BOX8-H0-MV1.5	7.726	7.709	9.930	11.889	
	BOX8-H0-MV2	7.758	7.734	9.964	11.914	
	BOX8-H0-MV3	7.738	7.724	9.934	11.884	
Loading beam	BOX-T (A)	15.200	15.263	30.538	30.550	
	BOX-T (B)	15.200	15.225	30.550	30.500	

The manufacturer provided the material certificate for all the unique plates of the specimens. From the load-bearing point of view the material behaviour of four plates are important to each specimen, the two webs (W1, W2) and the two flanges (F1 and F2). After the loading experiments altogether 40 coupon specimens were cut out from the specimens from 20 different positions (with limited or having no plastic deformations). This is not covered all the different unique plates but covered all the different type of materials that were used during composition based on the material certificates. Based on the knowledge which plates were made from the same materials and using the results of the coupon test, the yield stress of the 56 unique plates is identified and summarized in *Table 3*.

Table 3. Yield stress [MPa] of each plate of the specimens

Loading type	Specimen code	Web, W1	Web, W2	Top flange, F1	Bottom flange, F2
M-type	BOX4-355-M	353	424	474	474
	BOX4-700-M	785	785	756	721
	BOX4-H1-M	366	366	595	595
	BOX4-H0-M	420	420	756	732
	BOX6-H0-M	382	382	756	721
	BOX8-H0-M	400	400	740	721
MV-type	BOX4-H0-MV1	414	414	756	721
	BOX4-H0-MV1.5	414	386	756	721
	BOX4-H0-MV2	414	414	756	721
	BOX4-H0-MV3	413	413	740	720
	BOX8-H0-MV1	400	400	756	721
	BOX8-H0-MV1.5	400	400	756	721
	BOX8-H0-MV2	400	400	798	807
	BOX8-H0-MV3	400	400	740	721

4 TEST SET-UP AND MEASUREMENTS

4.1 General set-up

The general test set-up is shown in *Fig. 2*. The M-type specimens are subjected to 4-point loading (4P) creating a constant bending moment zone. The MV-type specimens are subjected to 3-point loading (3) creating a combined bending moment and shear force in the loaded specimens. The loaded specimens are connected to one (for MV-type) or two (for M-type) strong beams with a

reference length of 3500 mm. These beams are referred as BOX-T and its dimensions are also introduced in *Chapter 4*. The test set-ups on photos for the two different arrangements are shown in *Fig. 3*.

Fig. 2. General test set-up for M-type and MV-type specimens

The loaded specimens and the BOX-T elements are connected by bolts through the 30 mm thick endplates. The connection was made by M27 and M30 bolts (with a diameter of 27 and 30 mm) having 10.9 material grade ($f_y = 900$ MPa, $f_u = 1000$ MPa). Generally, for the upper half of the connection (so in the compression side) the M27 bolts are used and for the lower half (tensioned side) the M30 bolts are used. The load was applied by hydraulic jack(s). Generally, one jack is applied, but for some of the MV-type specimens two parallelly connected hydraulic jacks were used to be able to reach the ultimate load. Under the hydraulic jacks a load-distributing beam is used to spread the load uniformly on the top edge of the loaded endplate(s). The arrangement of the loading system is also shown in *Fig. 3*. Under one hydraulic jack a force measuring cell was used to detect the applied load during the tests.

Fig. 3. Real test set-up for a) M-type specimens; b) MV-type specimens

4.2 Measuring sensors

Linear displacement transducers (LVDTs) were used to detect the deflections and other displacements of the specimens at several positions during the tests. For M-type test set-ups these are shown in *Fig. 4*. These figures show all type of LVDTs, but not all of them were used for every test set-up. The global vertical displacements (VD) are measured in three positions, the lateral displacements (LD) of the endplates are measured in four positions, these are used to detect any twisting of the elements. The local vertical displacements of the top flange (LVD) were measured in three positions, the fix point for these sensors is set up on the load-distributing beam, therefore, the global displacement is not measured with these sensors. These data can be used to detect the local buckling failure of the top flange, using the difference of the reading between LVD-2 and the other

two LVD sensors. The axial position of these LVD sensors was in the middle of the specimens for three specimens, for the other three specimens these measurements were made 230 mm far from the endplate. At the A-side support the compression of the support (S) was also measured. This was measured in two positions (S-A1 and S-A3) initially, but during the first two tests it was observed that there is an initial gap between the top part of the connected endplates which is closing during the loading. Therefore, instead of S-A3, the gap between the end-plates on the B-side was measured for the last four M-type tests.

For MV-type test set-ups the arrangement of the LVDT sensors is shown in Fig. 5. These figures show all type of LVDTs, but not all of them were used for every test set-up. The global vertical displacements (VD) are measured in two positions, the lateral displacements (LD) of the endplates are measured in two positions. The gap between the connected endplates were measured for three specimens in the same way as it was measured for the M-type specimens. The eight MV-type specimens are initially grouped into three groups based on the expected failure modes, these are moment failure (M), shear failure (V) and moment-shear interaction failure (V-M), the arrangement of the LVDT sensors measuring local displacements was designed based on the expected failure mode. For those specimens where shear or interaction failure was the expected failure mode, the local horizontal displacement of the web is measured in five positions. For those specimens where moment or interaction failure was the expected failure mode, the local vertical displacement of the flange is measured in three positions for (M) failure and in one position, at the middle of the flange for (V-M) failure. These measurement points were generally 15 cm from the endplate, but for the BOX4-H0-MV3 specimen this distance was 50 cm to match to the expected failure.

Fig. 4. General LVDT arrangement for M-type test set-up (side view).

Fig. 5. General LVDT arrangement for MV-type test set-up (side view).

Alongside the LVDTs, several strain gauges were used to measure the strains at several positions. The general strain gauge arrangement is shown in Fig. 6, which shows all type of strain gauges, but not all of them were used for every test set-up. For M-type specimens only one directional (1D) strain gauges were used to detect the longitudinal strains and stresses, but for MV-type specimens

rosette type, three directional (3D) strain gauges were also used to detect the shear strains and stresses beside the longitudinal readings. The eight MV-type specimens are initially grouped into three groups based on the expected failure modes, these are moment failure (M), shear failure (V) and moment-shear interaction failure (V-M), the strain gauge arrangement was designed based on the expected failure mode. For those specimens where shear failure was the expected failure mode, two cross-sections are measured, the cross-section 250 mm far from the endplate to detect the same moment behaviour that is detected for the other specimens and a cross-section 750 mm far from the end of the specimen to detect the behaviour where the shear failure is expected to occur.

Fig. 6. General strain gauge arrangement for M- and MV-type test set-up (side view).

5 LOADING PROCESS AND RESULTS

For all specimens a pre-loading process is applied to reach first 50 kN, then 100 kN, for BOX4-H1-M specimen the pre-loading reached 200 kN. The loading speed was approximately the same, about 1 kN/s for all specimens. In present paper only some of the results are shown because of limited page number, but in the presentation several more diagrams will be shown. Fig. 7 shows the force-vertical displacements diagrams for all specimens. The results show that the overall stiffness of the full test set-up was similar for all M-type tests, independently from the examined specimen (it proves the effect of the bolted joint on the stiffness).

Fig. 7. Force-vertical displacement curves a) for M-type specimens; b) for MV-type specimens

Based on the lateral displacement readings the twisting angle of the specimens is calculated and it has been observed that twisting during test was not relevant. Based on the local vertical displacements on the flanges of the M-type specimens the normalized local vertical displacement of

the middle of the flange is calculated based on *Eq. (2)*. From the six M-type specimens the local buckling failure shape of the top flange was close to the local vertical sensors for only the BOX4-H0-M specimen, for this case the corresponding diagrams clearly shows the propagation of the local buckling, see in *Fig. 8 c)*. Similar behaviour was observed for the MV-type specimens as well.

$$LVD_{mid-flange} = LVD_2 - \frac{LVD_1 + LVD_3}{2} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 8. a) bending type failure of BOX4-H0-M; b) shear type failure of BOX4-H0-MV1.5; c) force diagram in function of normalized local vertical displacement of top flange for BOX4-H0-M specimen.

The recorded strains from the strain gauges show reliable results that can be effectively used for the validation process of a numerical model. A representative bending and shear failure mode are shown in *Fig. 8 a)* and *b)*. Beside the measured displacements and the strain values the most important data of the experiments are the maximum reached load, which can be considered as the load resistance of the specimens. The maximum applied load is summarized in *Table 4*. From the applied load the bending moment and shear force in the critical cross-section is also calculated and presented in the table. For MV-type specimens the critical cross-section is defined 25 cm far from the applied load position.

Table 4. Experimental resistance of examined specimens

Loading type	Specimen code	Max force (<i>F</i>) [kN]	Bending moment (<i>M</i>) [kNm]	Shear (<i>V</i>) [kN]	Calculated pure bending resistance [kNm]	Difference of bending resistance *
M-type	BOX4-355-M	485.26	849	0	822	103%
	BOX4-700-M	720.39	1231	0	1246	99%
	BOX4-H1-M	575.59	1007	0	990	102%
	BOX4-H0-M	703.63	1261	0	1315	96%
	BOX6-H0-M	745.25	1304	0	1377	95%
	BOX8-H0-M	817.77	1431	0	1485	96%
MV-type	BOX4-H0-MV1	798.16	466	621	-	-
	BOX4-H0-MV1.5	773.94	677	542	-	-
	BOX4-H0-MV2	854.88	952	544	-	-
	BOX4-H0-MV3	777.98	1152	419	-	-
	BOX8-H0-MV1	1901.22	1109	1479	-	-
	BOX8-H0-MV1.5	1410.14	1234	987	-	-
	BOX8-H0-MV2	1191.74	1327	758	-	-
	BOX8-H0-MV3	899.09	1331	484	-	-

* experimental bending resistance / calculated bending resistance

In order to evaluate the reliability of the experimental results we have determined the pure bending resistance of the M-type specimens based on the elastic-plastic concept that is proposed by several researchers such as Veljkovic and Johansson (2). For the analytical calculation of the bending resistance, we have not used simplified equations such as the ones that are proposed by some researchers (2, 14), since those are not applicable for sections with cross-section class 4. But performed the calculation based on the force and moment balance equations, taking into account the

partial elastic-plastic condition of the web and the reduction in the cross-section due to being cross-section class 4. Based on these calculation the obtained resistance values are very close to the experimental values as it is presented in *Table 4*, the biggest difference is only 5%. This proves together the reliability of the experiments and the good applicability of the applied resistance calculation method. These control calculations are only made for the specimens that were loaded by pure bending moment. For hybrid cross-sections the resistance calculation for the bending-shear interaction is more complex and there is no clearly accepted good method in the literature, this is why the presented experiments carried out could be a good bases to analyse and evaluate this behaviour and propose applicable calculation method. These investigations will be carried out and presented in a forthcoming publication.

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